

Opportunities in Aligning Artificial Intelligence Use with Student-Centred Learning in Public Senior Schools in Gombe State, Nigeria

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This study examined the opportunities in aligning Artificial Intelligence (AI) use with student-centred learning in public senior secondary schools in Gombe State, Nigeria. Guided by one objective, one research question and one hypothesis, the study used a descriptive survey design using a mixed-methods approach. The target population consisted of 2,728 teachers and 432 school administrators across 144 schools. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 353 respondents for the quantitative survey, while 15 key informants were purposively selected for qualitative interviews. Data collection tools included a validated questionnaire and an interview guide, with a reliability coefficient of 0.83 using Cronbach's alpha. Quantitative data were analysed by mean, standard deviation and t-test, while qualitative data were analysed thematically. Findings indicated that AI can help personalize instruction, enhance student engagement, support early intervention for learning difficulties and reduce teachers' administrative workload. The findings also noted that AI promotes inclusivity, collaboration and classroom management, while emphasizing the need for offline functionality due to infrastructural constraints. The study concluded that AI offers significant opportunities for improving student-centred learning in Gombe State Nigeria. In future, long-term effect of AI on students' performance should be investigated. It recommended among others that government should design AI platforms to low-resource environments and school administrators should conduct campaigns and information sessions to promote understanding of how AI can reduce teacher workload, personalize instruction and improve classroom outcomes.

Keywords:
Opportunities,
Artificial
Intelligence,
Student-Centered,
Technologies,
Secondary School.

Introduction

Education is undergoing changes across the world with the spread of digital technologies, including Artificial Intelligence (AI). In many countries, AI is being used to improve teaching and learning by many tools such as adaptive

platforms, tutoring systems, predictive tools and automation. These tools are often linked to student-centred approaches, where learners are encouraged to take a more active role, learn at their own pace and work more collaboratively.

In developed countries, it seems AI has already been applied in areas such as personalised instruction, automated assessment and support for students with special needs. However, in many developing countries, including Nigeria, its use in schools still appears to be limited. Nigerian education appears to continue to struggle with large class sizes, teacher shortages, poor infrastructure and restricted access to digital tools. These challenges underline the need for alternative solutions such as AI, which may help teachers and schools improve learning in ways that are more efficient and better suited to student needs.

Gombe State, located in North-Eastern Nigeria, seems to be among the regions striving to improve the quality of public education amidst socio-economic and infrastructural challenges. It is critical to address these challenges particularly at the senior secondary school level. It marks the final phase of secondary education and most of the time serving students ages range from 15 and 18. This stage comprises the last three years of formal schooling before gaining admission into tertiary education or vocational training and is designed to prepare students for university entrance examinations, technical careers or direct employment. It features more specialized and subject-focused curricula compared to basic education (FRN, 2014). Yet, public senior secondary schools in the state seems to be often characterized by under-resourced classrooms, limited access to digital tools and a predominantly traditional, teacher-centred approach to instruction. These challenges appear to hinder the effective delivery of quality education and limit the adoption of innovative, student-centred practices that could better prepare students for 21st-century demands.

Despite the state government efforts to implement technology-based initiatives through

various education reforms, the integration of AI appears to remain largely untapped or misunderstood among educators and school leaders. In fact, the state's increasing student population and growing demand for inclusive and equitable learning experiences call for the adoption of creative learner-focused solutions. AI seems to offer promising opportunities to bridge this gap by enabling automated feedback, adaptive learning and real-time student monitoring all of which are essential features of student-centred education.

Prior research carried out in related settings shows that AI has been progressively studied as a tool for improving equity and learning efficiency in resource-constrained environments. For instance, studies in sub-Saharan Africa have reported that AI-powered tutoring and feedback systems can help mitigate the effects of teacher shortages, while adaptive platforms have shown promise in supporting learners in large and heterogeneous classrooms (Okonkwo & Ade-Ibijola, 2021). Similarly, AI technologies enable personalized learning experiences by analyzing individual student patterns, strengths and weaknesses to customize educational content, ensuring equal opportunities for all learners regardless of their starting point (Pawar & Khose, 2024; Roshanaei Olivares & Lopez, 2023). Nevertheless, few studies have systematically analysed AI's role in promoting student-centred learning in Nigerian secondary schools.

The **National Policy on Education** affirms the need to provide education that is functional, practical and oriented toward self-realization and technological advancement. Specifically, the policy advocates for the incorporation of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) at various stages of education to improve teaching and learning, promote creativity and equip learners with

21st-century skills (FGN, 2014). Using AI as an advanced component of ICT directly supports this vision and if utilized properly, it can positively change learning in schools.

Literature Review

AI is increasingly influencing how teaching and learning are carried out, instead of relying on uniform instruction, AI systems allow teachers to adjust learning according to what each student's needs, by analysing learner data, providing immediate feedback and adjusting the pace or type of content as required. Gligorea et al. (2023) and Saraswat (2024) both reported that such systems make learning environments more flexible and responsive, which often leads to stronger student engagement and better outcomes. UNESCO-UNEVOC (2019) described AI in education as including tools such as chatbots, intelligent tutoring systems and analytics for monitoring learners. Saraswat (2024) also showed that, in higher education, AI-based teaching methods increased participation and improved results by giving students extra support when needed. In this way, AI technologies are not only changing instructional methods but also supporting the broader idea of student-centred education.

Personalization of instruction through AI-powered adaptive learning systems analyse learners' interaction data and adjust instructional content, pace and assessment strategies in real time to meet individual learning needs. Gligorea et al. (2023) conducted a systematic review of 63 studies and found that machine learning and AI algorithms significantly enhance engagement, academic achievement and the personalization of learning in e-learning environments. In similar vein, Chakraborty (2024) highlights that the use of generative AI in education fosters personalized,

adaptive and experiential learning, equipping students with the future-ready skills necessary in an evolving digital economy. This viewpoint aligns with the observations by Holstein and Doroudi (2021), who emphasize that AIED holds transformative potential to promote educational equity and inclusion by making instruction to meet the different needs of all learners, which include those in underserved or marginalized communities. Such personalization is particularly relevant to public senior secondary schools in regions like Gombe State, where disparities in access and learning outcomes persist.

However, recent research also reveals significant negative impacts of AI on student-centred learning. Studies indicate that excessive reliance on AI technologies can lead to passive learning experiences and hinder the development of students' knowledge systems and cognitive abilities (Potter, Robert & Frank, 2024; Cui & Alias, 2024). Key concerns include personal disconnection, lack of customization, dissemination of inaccurate information, and privacy and security issues, with the latter being identified as the most significant negative impact (Abd Rahman et al., 2023). While AI offers benefits like personalized learning and immediate feedback, the risk of over-dependence threatens meaningful human interactions and deeper understanding in educational settings (Potter et al., 2024).

The concept of student-centred education, which is central to this study, has been widely acknowledged in global education discourse. UNESCO (2021) defines student-centred education as putting the learner at the heart of the educational process, spotting their unique potential and fostering conditions for self-realization and societal contribution. This

model links education to broader human development goals, including equity, lifelong learning and social justice. Reimers and Schleicher (2020) similarly argue that student-centred systems empower learners to contribute meaningfully to a sustainable and inclusive future, grounded in values such as dignity and equity. In the Nigerian setting, Olatunde-Aiyedun (2024) revealed that AI integration significantly enhanced student engagement and academic performance. This demonstrates the potential importance of implementing similar strategies at the secondary school level, especially when these are situated within the principles of student-centred learning. According to Khosravi et al. (2023) learner sourcing when combined with AI technologies, promotes deeper engagement, critical thinking and a sense of ownership over the learning process.

Statement of the Problem

The shift toward student-centred learning is a critical priority in modern education, particularly in addressing diverse learning needs and promoting active student engagement. In Nigeria, however, many public secondary schools, especially in states like Gombe, still seems to rely heavily on teacher-centred approaches that limit student autonomy, creativity and participation. With the rapid global advancement of AI, there are emerging opportunities to support student-centred practices through personalized learning, intelligent tutoring and real-time feedback. Unfortunately, the integration of AI in Gombe State's public senior secondary schools appears to remain minimal and largely underexplored. Without deliberate exploration of these opportunities, public schools in Gombe risk falling further behind in preparing students for a future shaped by digital technologies and personalized

learning systems. To fill the gaps, this study investigated the opportunities in aligning AI use with student-centred learning in public senior secondary schools in Gombe State Nigeria.

Objective of the Study

The objective of this study explored:

1. The opportunities AI presents for enhancing student-centred learning in public senior secondary schools in Gombe State Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research question guided this study:

1. What opportunities does AI present for supporting student-centred learning in public senior secondary schools in Gombe State Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

This study was guided by the following hypothesis:

1. There is no significant perceived opportunity for AI to enhance student-centred learning in public senior secondary schools in Gombe State, Nigeria.

Methodology

This study used descriptive survey design using a mixed-methods approach, that is both quantitative and qualitative approach. The target population consisted of 3,160 teachers and administrators from 144 public senior secondary schools across Gombe State's 11 LGAs. A sample of 353 respondents was selected through multi-stage sampling. First, three LGAs, Akko, Funakaye and Gombe were purposively selected because they represent urban, semi-urban and rural educational settings respectively. Then, 321 teachers and 32 administrators were

proportionately and randomly selected from 15 stratified schools to ensure balanced representation across different school categories. A total of 316 valid responses were obtained from the 353 questionnaires administered. For the qualitative component, 15 key informants from AI/ICT-related units and school administrators were purposively selected from the same LGAs. Data collection tools included a 10-item structured questionnaire and a semi-structured interview guide, both addressing **opportunities offered by AI**. The questionnaire used a five-point Likert scale. Expert validation ensured clarity, and a pilot test refined the tools. Reliance on questionnaire responses may introduce social desirability bias, where teachers and administrators might provide responses they believe are expected rather than their actual

views or experiences. As a result, the use of both quantitative surveys and qualitative interviews provided methodological triangulation, which enhances validity by corroborating results from multiple sources. A Cronbach's Alpha of 0.83 confirmed acceptable reliability. The quantitative data were analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation with 3.0 as the decision benchmark, and inferential statistics of t-tests at the 0.05 level of significance. While qualitative data were analysed thematically for in-depth understanding.

Findings

Research Question 1: What opportunities does AI present for supporting student-centred learning in public schools in Gombe State Nigeria?

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics on Opportunities of AI in Student-Centred Learning in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Gombe State

S/N	Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
1	AI tools help personalize learning experiences in order to meet the individual needs of students in your school.	4.11	0.74	Agree
2	AI has the potential to improve student engagement by providing interactive and adaptive learning content.	3.97	0.81	Agree
3	AI technologies can support early identification and intervention for students with learning difficulties.	3.89	0.85	Agree
4	AI can enable teachers to focus more on mentoring and guiding students rather than routine tasks.	3.75	0.89	Agree

S/N Item	Mean	Std. Deviation	Decision
5 AI-based systems can assist in monitoring students’ progress and providing timely feedback.	4.02	0.79	Agree
6 Local content can be integrated into AI platforms to promote culturally relevant and context-specific learning.	3.68	0.91	Agree
7 AI can help reduce teacher workload by automating administrative and assessment tasks.	3.93	0.82	Agree
8 AI-powered translation or voice tools can support students with language barriers or special needs.	3.70	0.87	Agree
9 Student-centred AI can help create more inclusive learning environments in public secondary schools.	3.84	0.83	Agree
10 The use of AI in education can enhance collaboration between teachers, students and parents.	3.86	0.85	Agree
Grand Mean	3.88		Agree

Source: Field Work, 2025.

Table 1 revealed that respondents generally have a positive perception of the opportunities offered by AI in promoting student-centred learning in public senior secondary schools in Gombe State. With a grand mean of 3.88, all the items presented were rated above the midpoint. The highest mean score of 4.11 was recorded for the item stating that AI tools can help personalize learning experiences to meet the individual needs of students. This was followed by the view that AI-based systems can assist in monitoring students’ progress and providing timely feedback, with a mean of 4.02, and the belief that AI can improve student engagement through interactive and adaptive content, with a mean of 3.97. Other items also

received favourable responses, including the potential of AI to reduce teacher workload, support early identification of learning difficulties, and enhance collaboration among teachers, students and parents. Although the item on integrating local content into AI platforms had the lowest mean score of 3.68, it still fell within the “agreed” range.

The following structured interview questions were asked:

1. What probable benefits can AI give in teaching and learning, particularly in supporting teachers to reduce workload or improve classroom management?
2. What kinds of AI-based platforms or tools would be most useful in your school’s context?

Table 2: Responses from Structured Interview on Opportunities of AI in Student-Centred Learning

Theme	Illustrative Quote
Reduction of teacher workload	“AI can help teachers save time by marking assignments or providing feedback automatically.” – Principal, Akko
Support for personalized learning	“AI can give students extra exercises based on their level while the teacher focuses on the class.” – ICT Teacher, Funkaye
Need for offline-capable tools	“We need AI platforms that can be downloaded and used offline because many schools don’t have reliable internet.” – ICT Teacher, Gombe

Source: Field Work, 2025.

Table 2 revealed one of the major themes identified is the reduction of teacher workload. A principal from Akko noted that AI can assist teachers by automatically marking assignments and providing feedback. Another significant theme is the support for personalized learning. An ICT teacher from Funkaye explained that AI can offer tailored exercises to students based on their individual learning levels, enabling the teacher to concentrate on managing the classroom as a whole. A third theme is the

need for offline-capable AI tools. An ICT teacher from Gombe emphasized the importance of having AI platforms that can function without internet connectivity, noting that many schools lack reliable access to the internet. Interview data supported the questionnaire results.

H01: There is no significant perceived opportunity for AI to enhance student-centred learning in public senior secondary schools in Gombe State, Nigeria. The summarized results of the analysis are presented in table 13.

Table 3: T-Test on Perceived Opportunity for AI to Enhance Student-Centred Learning in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Gombe State

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-cal	t-crit	P-value	Decision
AI Opportunity Score	316	3.88	0.49	315	27.94	±1.97	0.000	Reject

Source: Field Work, 2025.

Table 3 showed that the mean score of respondents was 3.88 with a standard deviation of 0.49. The calculated t-value was 27.94, which is far greater than the critical t-value of ±1.97 at 315 degrees of freedom. The p-value obtained was 0.000 far less than the 0.05 level of significance. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. This indicated that there was a significant perception among

respondents regarding the opportunity for AI to enhance student-centred learning in public senior secondary schools in Gombe State Nigeria.

Discussion

The findings revealed that AI helps personalize instruction, reduce teacher workload, monitor student progress, enhance collaboration and have the ability to reflect local content and context. However, it also revealed that there is a

need for AI tools that can function offline due to unreliable internet access in many schools. It showed statistically significant belief in the potential of AI to enhance student-centred learning in public senior secondary schools in Gombe State Nigeria. The findings of this study align with the work of Saraswat (2024), who found that AI-driven pedagogies in higher education enhance student engagement and improve learning outcomes through personalized scaffolding and immersive learning experiences. Similarly, Gligorea et al. (2023), in a systematic review of 63 studies, reported that machine learning and AI algorithms significantly improve engagement, academic achievement and the personalization of learning within e-learning environments. In the same vein, Chakraborty (2024) emphasized that generative AI fosters personalized, adaptive and experiential learning, thereby preparing students with future-ready skills required in the digital age. This perspective is further supported by Holstein and Doroudi (2021), who highlight the transformative potential of AI in education to promote equity and inclusion by making instruction to meet the different needs of all learners, which include those from underserved or marginalized communities. Collectively, these studies reinforce the view that AI play a crucial role in advancing student-centred learning.

Nonetheless, key concerns remain. Studies have identified challenges such as personal disconnection, lack of customization, dissemination of inaccurate information, privacy and security issues, with the latter being considered the most significant negative impact (Abd Rahman et al., 2023). While AI offers benefits like personalized learning and immediate feedback, the risk of over-dependence threatens meaningful human interactions and deeper understanding in educational settings (Potter et al., 2024).

Conclusion

The study showed that AI can strengthen student-centred learning in public senior secondary schools in Gombe State. Teachers and administrators agreed that it can help personalise instruction, reduce workload and support closer monitoring of students' progress, they also saw its value in making classrooms more collaborative and responsive to local needs. At the same time, the research revealed that poor internet access remains a major challenge, limiting the use of many AI platforms. Therefore, the study indicated that AI offers opportunities for improving teaching and learning in Nigerian schools, but its benefits will only be realised if practical issues such as infrastructure, access and teacher readiness are addressed. AI should not be seen as a replacement for teachers, it can serve as a supportive tool for making learning more student-centred and effective.

Recommendation

The following recommendation was made:

1. Government should develop AI platforms that can work offline or with low internet bandwidth, so that schools in rural and low-resource areas are not left behind. School leaders should organise campaigns, workshops and information sessions to help teachers and communities understand how AI can support teaching, reduce workload and improve classroom practices. Regular and practical training should be provided to teachers to build their skills in using AI tools in a way that fits the local school context. Also, developers and policymakers should ensure that AI platforms reflect Nigerian cultural and educational realities, so that content is relevant and meaningful for learners.

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